

‘SOCIO- ECONOMIC PERSPECTIVES IN THE GROWTH OF SYSTEM OF EDUCATION AT THE SUNDARBANS IN WEST BENGAL, INDIA.’

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ABSTRACT

The research study is entitled Socio-Economic perspectives in the growth of system of education at the Sundarbans in West Bengal, India. The researcher has deeply examined various important issues related to the Sundarbans region, with special attention to how the Sundarbans region was created and its development. The researcher has deeply investigated the crisis-ridden areas of the Sundarbans region where settlement has developed slowly and the development of the Sundarbans region is based on a weak economic rural agricultural system. The researcher are delving deeper into these issues and to shed light on them. The researcher wants to show how the Sundarbans region is a collection of Sundari trees and other trees, with rivers, canals, streams, ponds, and reservoirs spread all around like the veins and arteries of the human body. The entire Sundarbans region is thus standing on a critical communication system. A look at how a rural agricultural society has developed in the Sundarbans region, which is characterized by saline soil, brackish water, and a climate that is difficult for human habitation. The researcher seeks to show how colonial rule was created in the Sundarbans region and the historical economic and social context in which the agricultural system developed. The East India Company's goal was to collect revenue from the Sundarbans region and how they could expand the administration further. In that context, the commissioners of the Sundarbans appointed by the East India Company at that time, Claude Russell and Mr. Henkel, were given the responsibility of the Sundarbans on behalf of the East India Company. All these commissioners called auctions to convert the forest land of the Sundarbans into agricultural land and distribute it to the zamindars and lotdars for the purpose of collecting revenue. At that time, people from different areas of Krishnanagar, Kolkata, and Midnapur, who were landowners and economically influential, participated in acquiring land. Then, after they took over the land from the British government, they hired agents to gather woodcutters to convert the forested land into agricultural land. In this way, forest land was gradually converted into agricultural land. The researcher has highlighted, through in-depth investigation, all the significant factors behind the development of a weak agricultural-based social system, especially this rural agricultural-based social system. The researcher seeks to show how the lot system was created and how that lot system was distributed among various lotdars and zamindars and sheds light on how they were used. The researcher wants to show how to build an education system within that weak economic social system. In that time, a small number of people who were from East Midnapore, West Midnapore, Howrah and undivided Bengal, started living here. How did the education system develop the researcher sheds light on that issue. At that time, some social workers, educated people, teachers and people who were passionate about education came forward with kerosene lanterns in their hands and went from

village to village to gather students. They gathered students and started their studies on their own initiative in various club houses and collapsed buildings. Thus, gradually, many private institutions such as Ramkrishna Mission, Bharat Sevashram and Christian Missionaries also came forward to develop the educational system in the Sundarbans region. Along with this, ordinary people also came forward. Various social workers also tried to develop literacy and education systems in the Sundarbans region through various methods. In this way, the economic structure of the Sundarbans region developed through a weak rural agricultural system. The present researcher sheds light on how the education system in the Sundarbans region has developed of this weak rural economy. The researcher gathered various information from primary and secondary sources. At the same time, the researcher adopted a qualitative research method. The researcher collected data from various books and census reports, etc., and through his own questionnaires. In this way, the researcher presents the true picture of the development of the agricultural economic system and education system in the Sundarbans region through his discussion. He explained the past of the Sundarbans region where people live in conditions fraught with poisonous snakes, insects, crocodiles, tigers and other dangers, with isolated communication systems.

OPERATIONAL TERMS: PATHSHALA, TOLL SYSTEM, LOTDAR, ZAMINDAR, ISLAND, RECLAMATION, ARKATHI.

1.1 INTRODUCTION:

Humans are social creatures. Society is made up of humans. Therefore, relationships between people in society are based on various factors. The economic base is also an important element in it. Not only is the foundation of the economy important, but it also requires social education, technology, science, art and culture to create a beautiful social system with people. All these elements make up society and people. So, society is involved in every aspect like this. The social system is woven together like threads or yarns, each thread forming a cloth. Also this social state exists by maintaining its own dynamics and balance. Every element of society is interconnected in maintaining this dynamic and balance. Similarly, economic factors, religious factors, cultural factors, educational factors, and so on, all these factors together maintain the dynamic of the social system. Education is an element without which the progress of society is not possible. So education brings consciousness and education brings emotional power. With this power of consciousness and emotion, the social system creates powerful bonds among the people. We live in a social system and if we do not think rationally about how people behave and interact with each other, then we are creating obstacles to the proper balance of that social system. So, apart from education, everything in the social system, human relationships and consciousness, is the product of education. Also with the development of this education system, economic strength is very much needed. Because without economy or economic power, one can never become a skilled and educated person. Therefore, to build a technologically strong social system, we need people who are technologically strong. Only then can this triangular relationship between education, economy, and society be developed properly. So society, education, economy and people are all interconnected like threads. Swami Vivekananda says that 'Education is the manifestation of perfection already in man'. Not only that, he talked about 'man-making' education. In other words, to build a nation, you need people, and to become a

human being, you need to be educated to become a human being. He wanted to mean a compassionate person with an educated mind, intelligence, and understanding, not a human being with flesh and blood, eyes, nose, and ears. So, man making education is very necessary for building society. The society we live in today is a modern society, and behind the development of this modern society is modern education and man-making education. So, Swami Vivekananda rightly said that to build society, people with a man-making education are needed to build society. Of course, it is true that the cost or expense of educating people in society is an inevitable condition. Because being recognized as educated and technically trained requires spending money. Or, to be highly educated, money is definitely needed, so education in a social system is a combination of money, religion, culture, and politics. Without economic element, no society can develop properly, not only that, but no individual can flourish his personality. So every element is important in society and is related to the life of the individual.

1.2 ECONOMICAL INTERPRETATION OF EDUCATION:

Economics is related to the education system and education. Because education cannot be developed easily without economy, even if it is developed, various problems may arise. In other words, it can be said that education is inextricably linked to economic relations. A strong education system cannot be built in a weak economic environment. Because a country that is economically weak also has a sufficiently and proportionately weak education system. In other words, it can be said that the most important factor that provides the most resources for the development of the educational structure and education system is the economy. A strong economy helps build a successful and robust education system. Because everyone's economy requires all the expenses that they incur or the expenses that they incur during their education. If all those education-related expenses or costs are not incurred, then education will remain unfinished. Therefore, to apply theoretical knowledge to practice, the relationship between the education system and economics must be linked. Otherwise, the education system will not be able to develop strongly. In other words, it can be said that the economic system is inextricably linked with the education system. By discussing these aspects, we can understand how the educational structure and the economic structure are interconnected.

Human capital theory: First of all, according to the human capital theory, it can be said that in order to improve human resources, the supply of economic resources is necessary. Because if we want to make human resources more effective and more efficient, then economic power is definitely needed. Man creates consciousness through their education and through that consciousness they can fully develop their personality. Also to fully develop that personality, higher education will require money, just as it will require higher education. Therefore, human resources have to be strengthened and strengthened through financing. From that perspective, economic wealth is related to human resource development. The development of society is not possible with theoretical knowledge alone, it needs practical knowledge along with it. Also that practical knowledge will depend on economic expenditure. Along with that, another thing needs to be mentioned that if individuals are more educated in society, then their productive capacity also increases through improved thinking. Therefore, higher education plays a significant role in helping a country achieve high income or economic power. Another point to note is that when

individuals in a society are highly educated, the scope of employment increases and the economic growth of the country occurs.

Costs and benefits of education:The economic explanation for the next setback is that if the first and benefit of education is seen, then there is definitely a benefit if the expenditure is on education. Because the more people in society are educated, the more money will be needed. As a result, the cost of education will increase. Meanwhile, as the cost of education increases, highly educated individuals create a rational social system and a technologically advanced social structure within society where productivity is at its highest level.

Education and economic growth:The next issue that needs to be highlighted is education and economic growth. That is, economic production will increase only when the people of the country become technologically strong. That is, technical knowledge increases productivity after receiving education at economic expense. In a country, a technically strong or trained workforce increases economic productivity through new and innovative ideas. This resulted in the country's economic growth and led to the development of industrialization and urbanization. Therefore, education does not just stop at increasing one's own knowledge and skills, but also technically skilled individuals play a positive role in the country's economic development and increasing national income.

Education and elimination of economic inequality:Another economical interpretation of education is that education and the elimination of economic inequality or discrimination are ongoing processes because if there is inequality in society, then society cannot progress. If citizens are educated, their economic earning power will increase. Suddenly, if citizens are well-educated, their economic productive power will increase and economic and social inequality will be eliminated. In this sense, education plays a significant role in eliminating social inequality, economic inequality, and all other social and temporal inequalities. Every social system is full of inequality. Also to eliminate this inequality, education is necessary because education makes people rational, intelligent, and helps them adapt to the environment. Not only that, education removes the differences between people due to various social reasons. Therefore, economic productivity or the economic aspect is highly related to education.

Education and economic strength:Education not only helps in increasing economic strength, but also builds better relationships with people. Humans are social creatures. Humans have to live in society. No human being can live alone. The society is closely connected with each other and moves forward by helping each other. Since the social system always runs on people, that is, the social system is built on people. So, everyone is involved in human relationships. That is why all people in the social structure are involved in economic activities for the purpose of their livelihood. Also to get involved in this economic activity, education is needed. Through education, various trainings, i.e. technical training, increase innovative power. Also with this innovative power, the country's economic production and other productive forces are greatly enhanced. As a result, society reached the peak of development. Therefore, since humans live in a social system, human society must be educated and at the same time, in order to get education, the cost of education must be incurred. That is, economic power will be required. So,

to build a good social system, we have to combine education with economy. Only then the education system becomes complete when the economic system also becomes progressive.

Investment Pattern: If the investment pattern is good, then the economic system improves. Because if the investment pattern is applied correctly in a country, then the production technique will increase. If economic power or money is invested in a factory properly, then that factory can be liberated. Therefore, it is better to use the appropriate money and earn money by finding labour or workers. So there should be an investment pattern in favour of a country that will help the country's development in terms of economic development.

Occupational Structure: In this case, to become economically strong, agriculture and industry must develop. If agriculture and industry are to develop and progress in agriculture and industry, then technological labour is needed. Therefore, without a technically skilled labour force, progress in agriculture and industry cannot occur. Therefore, for the progress of agriculture and industry, an occupational structure is needed, that is, the determinant of economic development is the occupational and working population of the country.

Market Expansion: In other words, the extent of market education is necessary because the market is essential for economic development and the development of the country. Economic development is not possible for any country without markets. Markets are needed to sell industrial and agricultural products. However, wealth will be distributed to the people and money will also flow in. Thus, the country's economy can be strengthened through the export-import nature of the foreign market.

Advancement of technology: With the advancement of technology, the country's economic progress is bound to change. The country's economic wheels will turn properly and vigorously if technological advancements occur. Without technological advancement, it is impossible for a country to achieve economic development in any way, whether in agriculture or in industry. Therefore, technology is used in every field for the development of society.

Development Planning: The fundamental planning of others is very important and necessary for the economic development of a country. Planning must always be done in a way that leads to economic development in the country's agriculture, industry and other sectors. That is, strategic planning is very important for economic development. Without strategic planning, economic development or national development is not possible.

1.3 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY:

The entire Sundarbans area is actually united economically, that is, in terms of agricultural economy. Their way of life began centered around an agricultural economy. This agricultural economy and way of life is inherited from them and has been going on for a long time, even today. It can be said that through this agriculture-based economy, the development of their society, roads, education, politics, culture, and social issues, everything stands still. Thus, their way of life and values have been based on an agricultural economy, through decades and centuries of hard work. So this is how they are used to their rural life being very simple and ordinary. They do not have high aspirations or high hopes, nor do they have the desire to become more and more financially strong. They are moving forward accepting that rural agricultural

economy, and in this way their culture and civilization are gradually advancing. Like a ladder of decay, the ordinary rural people of the Sundarbans have tried to develop social speakers beautifully, gradually moving from the lowest rung to the highest rung. If we look at the natural, geographical, and social conditions of the Sundarbans, we can see that the number of poor people and the poor class is high. Because all the economic classes that live here, most of them were fishermen until 100 years ago, the woodcutters, the 'Poundra community', the 'Nama Shudra' community, etc., arrived in this area earlier. Along with this, their occupation, that is, their economic means, was to sell honey and wood from the forest and natural resources, catch and sell fish, and do a small amount of farming. This was their way of life and profession, and they were in the same economic situation 100 years ago. But later, there were changes in the social situation, economic thinking changed, and mechanization in agriculture occurred. As a result, society, that is, the Sundarbans region, is gradually moving forward in the light of progress. However, the geographical and natural conditions were such that on one side the river was full of canals, on the other side the Bay of Bengal was surrounded by forests. These things involve the suffering of the people living in the Sundarbans. Then, the sessional tyranny of the lotdars and the zamindars is no less important, which completely destroyed the life of the common people in the midst of tyranny. Foreign rule, i.e. colonial rule, set their sights on the Sundarbans region for the purpose of collecting revenue. So on the one hand, colonial tyranny was desired, and later, the oppression of the landlords all combined to make their lives miserable. From this situation, people have gradually come forward through life struggles, risking their lives. They have grown up embracing the salty soil and salt water of the Sundarbans. Over hundreds of years, they have gradually developed the Sundarbans in their own way.

1.4 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM: It can be said that the Sundarbans region and the people of that region have come forward through various problems and they have come forward in terms of education and literacy. Through their struggle, they have overcome all the problems in their lives. Also by overcoming the problems, they have slowly developed their education system and educational structure. Almost every village in the Sundarbans region is cut off by rivers and canals. As a result, even though each village is disconnected, they remain culturally and geographically united. Nowadays, there is improved communication and bridges have been built over rivers and canals, and people-to-people relations have been established more strongly. Previously, the current situation was the opposite. In the past, communication was not at all terrible, there no advanced means of communication. People had to rely on boats to move around. The Sundarbans region has been struggling economically for a long time, that is, struggling to survive. The reason for this is that the geographical and social conditions are so terrible that through that social system, their rural economic system where people cannot eat properly twice a day. Those who have to go into the jungle for economic activities, risk their lives to travel from one place to another by river. It is seen that he left the house for economic activities. Perhaps their lives were lost in the river or in the jungle, in the face of a tiger. Thus their lives were spent in the terrible conditions hundreds of years ago and they have shaped people's social lives. It has affected not only social life but also economic, cultural, political and other aspects of life. As a result, the children of neighbourhoods and villages in the Sundarbans region, did not have access to literacy or education for hundreds of years, only a few local

social workers came forward. Along with how their lives are going, a democratic social system like India has also maintained the spirit of democratic mentality. There, the Panchayat system has come into power in the hands of the people. People are gradually becoming more conscious of democracy. Small markets have been created. People are moving the agricultural economy towards a market economy. In this way, this common mentality, that is, the mentality of unity, has been created in the Sundarbans region. Not only that, but their connection to the mainstream of economic and life struggle has led them to fight unitedly for a long time for all the development and love for the Sundarbans region. Thus, the Sundarbans area of India have gradually developed, their educational system, their political system, their democratic thought, their social struggle and everything.

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY: It can be said that the Sundarbans region and its social system are shaped by various rituals, customs, and other rules and regulations. These customs, traditions, and their continuity have bound their lives in all aspects. The people of the Sundarbans region cannot go beyond these customs and social behaviours, because these are their traditions and these traditions have served as values for them for centuries. As a result, they have influenced their daily thoughts and mindsets throughout their lives. Along with this, their social thoughts, social values, and morals have become based on the rural mentality. At the same time, religious and social customs have influenced their lives in every aspect. Their economic activities are slowly flowing with their daily demand in the society. This economic activity was nothing more than their farming. In some cases, since salty areas have salty water, salt production has been adopted as an economic occupation by ordinary people. But it is not possible to properly manage the journey through salt production, through the sale of wood, through the sale of honey, through this weak agricultural system. So they have to think that currently, the liberal economy and the transition from rural economy to urban economy are flowing in a new direction. Along with the changes in the social system, the market economy has changed people's lives and lifestyles. Because as mechanization and science gradually came into agriculture, agriculture has reached a more advanced level. As a result, people have money in their hands and people are gradually becoming economically strong. The economic sufficiency of people, which was not there 100 years ago, has become stronger in terms of their own thinking. But today, people have been able to create markets, selling their goods through small markets and bazaars in the villages, and they are connecting with the cities that have developed nearby. As a result, the economic landscape has changed, and if this economic landscape changes, their mentality and thinking are bound to change as well. Therefore, standing at the threshold of the 21st century, we have to think that the economic and social conditions of the Sundarbans region 100 years ago have changed a lot today. But our thoughts about the Sundarbans region, which has saline water and saline land that has affected human life in all aspects, Today, the Sundarbans region has come before us as an international issue. Because the Sundarbans region is a region where everything, economic, social, political, educational and cultural, has developed differently, the way of life of the people has been developed through the struggle for life. It is necessary to consider the historical and social context of how people have gradually progressed through the crises and pains of their daily lives, century after century, from an economic perspective. It is impossible to gain a proper understanding or knowledge about the Sundarbans region. If we look at the social system of the

Sundarbans people or those living in the Sundarbans region, we can understand the picture of the larger world through a miniature version of the world. Because the way the people of the Sundarbans region have managed their lives through struggle and gradually developed the Sundarbans society through it is truly remarkable. Therefore, the economic aspect of the Sundarbans region and its economic personality, social and educational foundations and political foundations have become very important in the current social system and have become relevant in the current century. Now the importance of the Sundarbans and the Sundarbans region is so great and has gained even more importance in terms of internationality.

1.6 Objectives of the Study:

- To explain how the Sundarbans region gradually developed.
- To explain the education structure in the rural economy of the Sundarbans region.
- To explain the literacy campaign in the Sundarbans region.
- To see whether the Lotdars and Zamindars contributed to education and literacy.
- To explain how the economic system of the Sundarbans region gradually developed.
- To explain how the rural economy was maintained for a long time.
- To explain how the Sundarbans region and the livelihoods of the people there have maintained their continuity.
- To explain how the people of the Sundarbans region have adapted to their weak economic system within the social system.
- To explain how the people of the Sundarbans region have linked their small-scale occupations to economic activities.
- To explain how the rural agricultural economy is transforming into a market economy.
- To explain how the land distribution system came from the East India Company.
- To explain how landlords and zamindars transformed the agricultural economy.
- To explain how the economy of colonial rule has affected the Sundarbans region for almost a hundred years.
- To explain how the economic struggle and misery of the ordinary people of the Sundarbans region have always been a constant companion to their livelihoods.
- To explain the suffering and economic hardships of the people of the Sundarbans region.
- To explain how the rural economy, the agricultural economy, has influenced the lives of people in the Sundarbans region for centuries and has caused them to live in hardship.

1.7 Research Questions of the Study:

- How was the Sundarbans region formed?

- How did the education system develop in the Sundarbans region with a weak economy?
- How was the literacy campaign launched on a weak economy?
- How did social welfare people come forward to develop the literacy situation?
- How was the agricultural economic system of the Sundarbans region maintained for a long time?
- How was colonial rule established in the Sundarbans region?
- How did the East Company distributed lands to the landlords and zamindars?
- How lotdars and zamindars exercised economic rule over the poor?
- How have the people of the Sundarbans region overcome their weak economic situation?
- How are the people of the Sundarbans region divided into social classes in economic terms?
- How did the Sundarbans region develop a market economy through economic struggle?
- How has scientific thinking influenced rural agriculture in the Sundarbans region?
- How has agriculture in the Sundarbans region been mechanized?
- How have the people of the Sundarbans region, with their education and thinking, brought their weak agricultural economy forward towards development?

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE:

Sneha Ghosh (2022) conducted a study entitled "Quest for Quality Education Status of School Grading System in Basanti Community Development Block within Indian Sundarbans Delta". The place of study area is Basanti block in Sundarbans. The author uses literature review and census report as a tool and talks about quality education. He says that there remains a great gap there he says that the thinking of education policy makers is about how current research is achieving student outcomes. The major findings were, the concept of quality in education started to modify any established after world conference on education for all scheduled in Jomtien, Thailand in 1990. After 10 years of it all education from held in 2000 in Dhaka reshaped the problem to concept of quality education. World education forum in Dhaka again proposed the ideas of quality education which are described as the input process output model by experts and the ratio between input and output defines as quality.

Sukumar Ghosh (2002) conducted a study entitled "An Investigation into the Impact of Literacy Status on Family Planning Programmes of Tribal People of Sundarbans Area". The major objectives of the study were, to find out the knowledge about the family planning program of different literacy status groups of scheduled Tribes people of Sundarbans area, to find out the attitude towards the family planning program of different literacy status groups of scheduled Tribes people of Sundarbans area, to find out the practical knowledge about different methods of family planning program of different literacy status groups of scheduled Tribes people of Sundarbans area, to find out the inter relationship among knowledge attitude methods

and mental health of scheduled Tribes people towards family planning programme according to their literacy status. The place of study selected by the researcher is sandesh khali block of sundarban area. The statistical tools of analysis by the author is method interview method and others. The major findings of the studies were, how the literacy and poverty is reigning in the study area and the population are growing day by day. Although the total literacy rate of sandeshkhali block is 39.57% what literacy rate of scheduled Tribes is only the total population growth rate sandeshkhali block is 25.16% in ten years where is schedule tribes growth rate of this block is 27.77% in 10 years. The situation creates and alarming and dangerous problems in the development of human like and society.

Pradip Kumar Mandal (2017) conducted a study entitled "Sundarbaner Jonojati O Loko Sanskriti Kuri Sotoker Samaj O Sanskritir Itihase Ekti Natun Drishtikon (The Tribal Groups of the Sundarbans and folk culture of the Society of the Tribal Groups In the 20th Century)". The major objectives of the study were, to study the sociology of folk culture and folk life of Sundarbans in the history of society and culture of the 20th century, to study recent regional history practice and regional history writing is particularly important in the context of how the work of real history writing has not been done. The place of the study is Sundarbans. Tools used by the author is personal interview and early literature review. Major findings of the study were, the rural society of the Sundarbans has given courage to closely distinguish the many details of people's life and to proceed with those experiences and the work of building history here, the local gods and goddess and their influenced to the tribal society. Earlier several books about Sundarbans have been published in Bengali and English languages, the role of these texts in advancing the author's thinking in the current research is certainly acknowledged.

Utpal Mandal (2014) conducted a study entitled "Sundarbaner Manus O Tar Jibon Darshan (The Inhabitants of the Sundarbans and Their Philosophy of Life)". The major objective of the study is, to study the philosophy of life of the peoples of the Sundarbans area. The place of the study is the Sundarbans, geographical location, topography and climate of each country or even a particular region specifically influences and control the history and lifestyle of the people of that country or region. Tool which questionnaires and the method used is survey method. The major findings of the study were the culture and the way of life of the people of the Sundarbans and their ancient ideas and thinking which in friends the total geographical area and the inhabitants of the area. The researcher concluded that, if we do not understand this individuality, we will not be able to fully understand the diversity of the country and the unity within diversity.

Senjuti Pal (2018) conducted a study entitled "A Socio-Economic Appraisal in the Context of Embankment Due to Natural Hazards in Selected Parts of Indian Sundarbans". The Major Objectives of the Study were, to understand the interdisciplinary nature of the river dynamics soil characteristics bio reserve structure of the society demography etc, to examine the status of the in bank balance and the possible alternatives of their maintenance, to SSD Dropbox of the existing system of embankment protection in relation to the local environment, and to formulate a policy to sustain such a huge population so that cyclonic for storms like Aila can do no harm to the dwellers further. The place of the study is the Sundarbans. The Researcher Used statistical tools for collection of data were, personal interview, collection of maps

collection of data from Census Office. The method used is survey method. The major findings of the study were, Sundarbans experience different kinds of hazards and approximately 5 million of local inhabitants just manage to survive against all odds. The reclaimed part is extremely vulnerable due to impact of climate change and increasing population density. Construction of environmental was the key to reclamation.

Suparna Bhattacharya (2021) conducted a study entitled "A History of the Social Ecology of Sundarbans the Colonial Period". The major objectives of the study the rationale behind pursuing the particular topic of research lies in understanding the importance and relevance of three most important aspects of the present work the uniqueness of the naturally resources of the ecosystem named Sundarbans understanding the philosophy of social ecology and its present day relevance with special reference to the Sundarbans and finally placing these aspects within the time theme of colonial period and era of great transformation in the history of Sundarbans. Regarding the unique region that is Sundarbans one must realize that it is a multifaceted land in many ways. It is the objectives of the research. The place of the research is Sundarbans comprises North and South 24 parganas. Tools used by the researcher for this purpose were, colonial diaries, survey reports, district hand books, travel books and novels. Major findings of the study were, very few over the colonial time frame in chronological order when you're important developments in the Sundarbans were taking place and which had deep ramifications for the future. Even if they do cover the period there is open a brief mention of the important events during the concern period. Hence one can say that there is a lack of any form of echoes. Study covering the history of social ecology of Sundarbans during British Times. 10 lakhs in the focus who is the present work strives to follow.

Aparna Mondal (2001) conducted a study entitled "Life and Culture in the Sundarbans 1770 - 1870". The major objectives of the study were, to study the origin of the Sundarbans which is a facility subject for studying the naturalist scientists and history, and to folk in the culture and the habitation of the or the way of life of the people of the Sundarbans area. The mystery of its urgent is equally alluring and it will ever remaining a matter of controversy. The researcher used the survey method. Major findings of the study were, as according to the researcher Sundarbans is the largest single unit luxury and mangrove vegetations of the world. And also giving some description about the Sundarbans with the help of old books and materials.

Swapan Kumar Mandal (2018) conducted study entitled "Sundarbaner Abad Bhumi O Tar Rajnaitik Prekkhapot: Prasanga Guasaba 1930 – 1970 (Agricultural Lands of the Sundarbans and Its Political Background: Context Guasaba 1930-1970)". The major objectives of the study were, to study local politics and the land mongers of the Sundarbans and their rules, to know about land expansion started in the Sundarbans region from the end of the 18th century on the initiative of the colonial rule, to know various experiments continued to expand the cultivated agricultural land of the Sundarbans throughout the 19th century. The place of the study is in Sundarban and specially the gosaba. The researcher used the survey method and collection of data through the interview procedure. In this way the author has discussed the period from 1930 to 1970 by dividing this trend of protest politics into two phases. The major findings of the research were from 1967 to 1970, the introductory political conflict between these two

adversaries reached its final form, the rich on the one hand and the workers on the other are opposites, the discussion selects the present nine islands of Gosaba, one of the blocks of Sundarbans, as the geographical area, and the search for the reasons for this strong land-centricity of local politics is the main topic of his research.

Purnima Basu (1999) conducted study entitled “A Study of Inspection and Supervision of Primary Schools in West Bengal Which Special Reference to the Sundarbans Region”. The major objectives of the study is, to emphasizes that the post-independence era of Indian education opened of a new vista mark by far reaching reforms and changes, to understand the overall directing this venture to make the educational system and heritage from the foreign rulers to free from its colonial character and to democratize it as an effective instrument for socio economic transformation, and to know the objectives of University grant commission and the Mudaliar commissions and their objectives. The place of study is the Sundarban region which comprises 19 blocks in the North 24 Parganas and the south 24 Parganas. The major findings of the study were, be a matter of great brigade that inspired a various changes and reforms undertaken in the field of education in free India. The other hand the government taken supplementary by a number of national policies on education. It is in such a background that Indian education past through a stage of reforms and changes which sort to grape with various critical probability aspects of education. This automatically accelerated and extended the field of educational investigations and research activities in a multi-dimensional way. It is in the wake up in your words that is humble research worker filled and hours within her to take up the area of educational inspection and supervision for investigation. This goes without saying that the inspection system in India owes its origin to the woods dispatch of 1854 during the British rule. The nature scope and content as well as the function of the instruction services reviving to almost and changed and hence regimented. The fearing to release the very objective which is supposed to be represent that is to maintain the quality of excellence of education.

Bansari Halder (2017) conducted study entitled "Sundarbaner Adibasi Samaj Aitihya O Adhunikata"(The Tribal Society of the Sundarbans it's Heritage and Modernity). The objectives of the study were to discuss about the indigenous communities living in the Sundarbans region, to study books on Sundarbans, to discuss about the society here, and about the tribal people living in the Sundarbans region who were not noticeable. The place of the study is the Sundarbans. Field survey method is adopted for the study. Personal interview method is used to collect the data. The major finding of the studies were two researchers have touched upon the life and livelihood of the tribal people living in the Sundarbans region in their writings. In addition, the two authors who have written about a tribal community in their articles have very little depth of content and the purpose of the author to research about the tribal people living on the banks of the river in the Sundarbans region.

3.0 DESIGN OF THE STUDY:

The researcher has to adopt a specific design to conduct the research. That is, the design has been adopted. The design has been adopted with an eye toward helping the researcher reach his or her goals and research direction. Therefore, the research methodology has been implemented

into reality, focusing on that design. This researcher conducted his research according to the research methodology and adopted grounded theory.

The design of a piece of research called as design of the study, which refers to the practical way in which the research was conducted according to a systematic attempt to generate evidence to answer the research question. The term "Research Methodology" is often used to mean something similar, however different writers use both terms in slightly different ways: some writers, for example, use the term "Methodology" to describe the tools used for data collection, which others (more properly) refer to as methods. But the term 'Design of the study' is most appropriate because it contains sampling techniques, source of data, procedure of data collection, tool of data collection of the study, and methodology of the study.

3.1 SOURCE OF DATA:

Secondary sources used to collect the data. Secondary data means data collected by someone else earlier by surveys, observations, experiments, questionnaire, personal interview, Government publications, websites, books, journal articles, and internal records etc.

3.2 METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

Interviews, old papers, magazines and newspapers. Also, various information was collected from websites. These have been adopted as methods. The current researcher has continued his work as usual, adopting all these methods.

Grounded theory research design is used in Qualitative Research Method to study the Sociological Perspectives in the Growth of System of Education at the Sundarbans. Grounded theory research is an inductive approach in which a theory is developed based on data. This is the opposite of the traditional hypothesis-deductive research approaches where hypotheses are formulated and are then tried to be proved or disproved. Grounded theory is based on theoretical and epistemological concepts with the possibility of sustained use in three methodological aspects: classic, Straussian and constructivist. In the present study Constructivist grounded theory method is used. Constructivist grounded theory is a qualitative research methodology that draws comparison between the ethical principles of deontology, utilitarian and virtue ethics, and individuals seek to understand the world in which they live and work.

4.0 ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF THE STUDY:

Various interviews, especially personal interviews and interview and survey methods, have been applied, as well as various information has been collected through the use of old documents. It can be seen that the educational structure or literacy structure that has developed in the Sundarbans region has been through a very long process. Because when the East India Company took over the responsibility of the Sundarbans region, the idea of clearing the forest was just beginning. From then on, people gradually began to settle down and from there, people felt the need for education and literacy along with their livelihood. The information obtained through various interview questionnaires and their answers, as well as information obtained from books, has been analyzed. Interviews were conducted with people, generally over the

years of 50, on the Sundarbans and their education system and the development of literacy structures. In that case, they expressed their opinions in a specific and well-considered manner. Now, the information obtained from them shows that culture and cultural elements play a significant role in developing learning structures. As soon as they felt the need for literacy, they took the initiative and united the democratic people, making the literacy and primary education campaign a success. However, the Ramakrishna Mission and various voluntary organizations were involved. Along with this, various social groups became involved in literacy and carried out this campaign through songs, plays, journeys, and streetcorner. However, some social groups or people who are interested in social welfare came forward with this.

5.0 FINDINGS OF THE STUDY:

1. It shows how the education system and structure developed in the Sundarbans region.
2. It shows how the educational structure of the Sundarbans region was developed through colonial rule.
3. It shows how the economic life of the common people in the Sundarbans region balanced their educational life.
4. Showing how small economic groups became aware of literacy.
5. It shows how the land system was distributed in the Sundarbans region under the rule of the East India Company.
6. It is being shown that land distribution is also about lotdars and zamindars and their roles.
7. Showing how people maintained their relationships amidst weak communication systems is a matter of literacy.
8. It shows how people have consciously promoted their economic activities, cultural activities which related to education, even in a weak economic structure.
9. Showing how the educational structure adapted to the social system of the time.
10. It is being shown that the children of the Sundarbans region, crossing the rivers and canals, have gradually become interested in education.

6.0 RECOMMENDATIONS BASED ON THE STUDY:

- Later, the government improved roads and connected every neighborhood and village.
- The agricultural land in the Sundarbans region has been developed scientifically.
- Primary schools have been built in various places.
- Girls' schools have been built in various places.
- Co-ed schools have also been built on the site of the demolition.
- English medium schools are currently being built.
- English medium schools have been created more for younger children.

- Various training colleges have been established.
- Many colleges have been created for graduation.
- A bridge has been built over the river.
- The roads are paved a lot.
- Paved roads have been built even in the most remote places in rural areas.
- The primary school has established.
- The infrastructure of primary schools has been improved.
- There are enough teachers in primary schools.
- Awareness camps have been organized for students.
- The government should make sure of the communication system.
- The government should start thinking of new ideas in the world.
- To cooperate in the establishment of other existing schools.
- Establishment of schools in accordance with National Education Policy.
- Government should provide proper grants or financial assistance.
- If the government does this properly, it will help the internal ones to improve.
- Establishment of Secondary and Higher Secondary Schools.

7.0 CONCLUSION:

The development of cold conditions was primarily due to the colonial rule, especially in the Sundarbans region, where wealthy landowners and economically powerful individuals played a role. Later, the common people took initiative and the government, together with the common people, adopted various education policies, which strengthened the education system. Another sign of this is that almost a century ago, the Ramakrishna Mission, the Christian Missionary and the Bharat Sevashram, extended a helping hand in the fields of social welfare and education and literacy. In addition, various theater and social workers also come forward to further advance the issue of education and literacy within the society. So a social system that was completely weak in terms of communication 100 years ago has now become strong, and even through that weak communication system, people have become culturally aware. The government, private institutions, the public, and various cultural activists have helped bring the Sundarbans region forward economically, in terms of education, and literacy. The contribution of those who do social welfare or love for society was no less than that of the activities.

Finally, it can be said that the way the education system and literacy structure has been developed in the Sundarbans region has been through many stages and through various difficulties.

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